

Public policies with a gender perspective in the prevention of adolescent pregnancy: courses of action for the rights of adolescents in Mexico.¹

Patricia Lorena Nieto Begné²

Atziri Moreno Vite³

Gabriela Yolanda Castañón García⁴

Summary:

Teenage pregnancy in Latin America and the Caribbean has become one of the main problems in terms of public health, social, economic, and political. The Latin American region has the world's second-highest teenage pregnancy rate (only behind Africa). On average, 18% of births are to women under 20 (United Nations Population Fund [UNFPA], 2020).

The primary purpose of this research is to present the findings of the analysis of the relationship between adolescent pregnancy and poverty in Mexico, particularly in the State of Hidalgo, as well as the economic, social, educational, and public policy factors that influence this issue.

This is a multifactorial phenomenon, where inequality, poverty, and lack of opportunities may impact a higher percentage rate of teenage pregnancy. Therefore, it is necessary to have public policies with a gender perspective, that is, governmental courses of action in this case to address the specific needs of a sector of the population (adolescent women and men) that guarantee their rights to live in a healthy and sustainable environment and in conditions that allow their development, well-being, healthy and harmonious growth, that address and contribute to the reduction of teenage pregnancy and propose actions to solve this serious problem.

Keywords:

Teenage pregnancy, poverty, rights, gender, public policies.

JEL: I3, I38, O1

¹ This paper contains parts of the research of the book chapter: Nieto Begné Patricia Lorena, Moreno Vite and Castañón García "*Economía, Pobreza y Políticas Públicas con Perspectiva de Género en la Prevención del Embarazo Adolescente a Nivel Subnacional: Caso Estado de Hidalgo*" published in the book *Temas Contemporáneos de Investigación en Economía y Políticas Públicas* (2022) Volume II. University of Guadalajara. ISBN: 978-607-571-508-7.

² M.A. in Political Science from the University of Oregon, United States. Director of the School of Social Sciences and Government (ECSG) Tecnológico de Monterrey, Campus Hidalgo, Mexico. ORCID:0009-0003-5503-6967

³D. in Economics from the Complutense University of Madrid, Professor at the School of Social Sciences and Government (ECSG), Tecnológico de Monterrey, Campus Hidalgo, Mexico.
ORCID: 0009-0002-7619-1299

⁴ D. in Political Science from the Sorbonne Paris I University, France, Professor at the School of Social Sciences and Government (ECSG), Tecnológico de Monterrey, Campus Hidalgo, Mexico.
ORCID: 0000-0002-6131-1043

Introduction

Teenage pregnancy in Latin America and the Caribbean is one of the main problems in terms of public health and social, economic, and political. The Latin American region has the second highest teenage pregnancy rate in the world (only behind Africa). On average, 18% of births are to women under 20 years of age (United Nations Population Fund [UNFPA], 2020).

It is a multifactorial problem that accentuates existing inequalities. Most teenage pregnancies occur in low- and middle-income countries. Latin America has 25% of its population between the ages of 15 and 29. A large part of its economically active population is made up of young people. This demographic bonus could be very positive for the region. However, young people face various adverse circumstances, such as poverty, discrimination, and lack of quality education and health, which hinder their full human development (UNFPA, 2020).

Adolescent pregnancy negatively affects different areas, among which are: permanence in school, not only present but also future income, access to specialized and quality recreational, social, and labor opportunities, and human development, as well as the fulfillment and respect of their human rights.

In the case of Mexico, one out of every five births registered in 2018 were births to girls and adolescents between the ages of 10 and 19 (UNFPA, 2020). Counting with one of the highest rates of teenage pregnancy within the OECD member countries. In the case of Hidalgo, the percentage of adolescent pregnancies during 2019 was 18.62% (Grupo Estatal para la Prevención del Embarazo en Adolescentes [GEPEA], 2020).

In this sense, the primary purpose of this research is to analyze the economic, educational, and public policy factors that impact this issue.

Methodology

In this study, quantitative elements are used to analyze the findings and to know the structural conditions of adolescent pregnancy, particularly in the State of Hidalgo. A descriptive analysis is proposed, aspects, dimensions, and components of the phenomenon to specify characteristics of this fact in a given context (Hernández and Mendoza, 2018). For this analysis, primary and secondary sources of information are used, mainly reports and previous research on the problem.

Analysis process

This research is divided into three sections. The first section analyzes economic development and its relationship with teenage pregnancy, emphasizing that it is a multifactorial phenomenon where inequality, poverty, and lack of opportunities can influence a higher percentage rate of teenage pregnancy. The second section reviews the issue of adolescent pregnancy in Mexico, studying the statistics of teenage pregnancy in Mexico, particularly in the State of Hidalgo. Finally, public policies are addressed, that is, governmental courses of action in this case to meet the specific needs of a sector of the population (adolescent women), and some proposals are elaborated to contribute to reducing teenage pregnancy.

1. Economic development and its relationship with teenage pregnancy

At the end of the 1970s, it became evident that progress in economic growth did not translate into social benefits. Starting in the 90's, there was a significant shift in the measurements of economic development, which had been characterized by proposing economic growth as the main objective.

In the 1990s, Amartya Sen proposed a new interpretation of development focused on its human dimension. Based on this proposal, the Human Development Index (HDI), a key indicator of economic development, was created in 1990. In Latin America, Chile ranks first in HDI (rank 42), Argentina in second place (rank 48), and Uruguay (rank 57) in third place. During 2019, Mexico had an HDI of 0.767, ranking 76th out of 189 countries. However, it should be clarified that in 2017 it was ranked 74th; in 2019, it fell two positions concerning 2017. Even

though Mexico remains within the group of countries with high human development, it should also be noted that the HDI value at the country level needs to reflect the high degree of heterogeneity that is experienced within the Mexican territory.

The United Nations Development Program [UNDP] (2015) identifies the HDI of federal entities and makes an international comparison. This study indicates that the states with the highest levels of human development in the country -the Federal District, Nuevo León, and Sonora- are similar to those of countries such as Andorra, Argentina, and Oman. In contrast, the lowest levels of development observed in Mexico, located in Chiapas, Guerrero, and Oaxaca, are similar to those of Gabon, Egypt, and Botswana.

In particular, according to the earlier study, the State of Hidalgo has a medium-level HDI.

The problem of unwanted early pregnancy is a global concern affecting developed and developing countries. Stern (1997) mentions that the most widely disseminated and scientifically supported argument is that adolescent pregnancy is a mechanism that contributes to the transmission of poverty. Because of their low level of education, adolescents have access to low-paying jobs with low purchasing power, which in turn leads to the children of these women not having access to good living conditions, so this situation is perpetuated as a vicious circle of poverty.

Villalobos-Hernández *et al.* (2015) indicate that for some decades now, it has been recognized that early motherhood occurs more frequently in low socioeconomic strata. The authors suggest that a mixture of factors perpetuates poverty, given that this population starts from precarious conditions, a social construction of gender, a lack of comprehensive sexual education, poor access to contraceptive methods, and few economic opportunities.

The relationship between socioeconomic conditions and adolescent pregnancies is shown by the significant gap in adolescent childbearing between developing and developed countries; in the former, 10 percent of minors give birth each year, compared to 2 percent in developed countries (WHO, 2020). Similarly, adolescents living in rural areas and coming from poorer households are more likely to have their first child before age 19 compared to adolescents living in urban areas and in better-off households (Haub, 2010).

2. Teenage pregnancy in Mexico

According to INEGI (2021), during 2006-2008, the teenage pregnancy rate was 70.9 per 1 000 women aged 15 to 19 years; from 2011-2013, it increased to 77.0 births, and during the years 2015 to 2017, it was 70.6 births. This makes Mexico one of the countries with one of the highest teenage pregnancy rates. It has the highest rate of all members of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development [OECD] (2017). The United Nations Population Fund [UNFPA] (2020) indicates that one in five births registered in 2018 in Mexico were births to girls and adolescents between the ages of 10 and 19.

According to the National Institute of Statistics and Geography [INEGI] (2021), the following shows the evolution of teenage pregnancy in Mexico. As can be seen, the percentage of adolescent pregnancies has been decreasing. However, the rate continues to be very high.

**Figure 1: Fertility rate of women aged 15 to 19 years old
2006-2008, 2011-2013, 2015-2017 (Per 1,000 females aged 15-19)**

Source: Own elaboration with data from INEGI (2021).

2.1 Adolescent Pregnancy in the State of Hidalgo.

At the national level, the average years of schooling in Mexico is 9.7 years. However, at the subnational level, the State of Hidalgo is slightly behind the average with 9.4 years of education. See Graph 2.

Figure 2: Level of schooling by State

Source: Own elaboration with data from INEGI (2020).

The factors associated with adolescent pregnancy in Mexico vary according to the context, i.e., whether the woman lives in an urban or rural area, whether she belongs to a high economic stratum or not, etc. Among some of the factors that have been identified are: a) the predominance to continue with the perpetuation of traditional values about sexuality and reproduction, b) the importance given to motherhood, and c) the inequity in the relationships that exist between men and women (Grupo Estatal para la Prevención del Embarazo en Adolescentes [GEPEA], 2020). Another exclusion data is the incidence of the indigenous population. A recent study shows the categorization according to the fertility rate, with more pregnancies occurring in municipalities with a larger indigenous population (red color). See Figure 1.

Figure 1. Map of teenage pregnancies, Hidalgo, 2019.

Source: (1) Vital Statistics 2019 (data file) accessed February 14, 2020. INEGI. (2) Targeting study based on SINAC 2019 (data file) Mineral de la Reforma, Hgo. (As cited in GEPEA *et al.*, 2020).

Adolescent childbearing is viewed as a disadvantage for several reasons, but the most important concern centers on the fact that early childbearing almost invariably places the future of young mothers and their children at social, economic, and educational risk.

In a study conducted in Tepeapulco, Hidalgo, during the period from 2000 to 2007, a total of 858 pregnancies of women under 19 years of age were recorded (Ortiz, 2016). In this period, there is an average of 83 pregnancies per year. That study asked pregnant adolescents in the town of Tepeapulco if they became pregnant they were studying, 85% responded that they were not studying and 15% that they were. It is worth mentioning that 32.5% of the population surveyed indicated they were single mothers. This figure is significant because it can be affirmed that the fact of having become pregnant so young increases their degree of vulnerability and leads to a lower level of education and socioeconomic status in general, an argument related to that which affirms that early motherhood is a mechanism for the transmission of poverty (Buvinic *et al.*, 1992).

In addition to these factors, there are external factors that have more to do with governmental or non-governmental actions for the prevention of adolescent pregnancy. That

is, with the measures that are taken in advance to address and prevent this critical public problem.

3. Public policies with a gender perspective for preventing adolescent pregnancy.

Authors such as Aguilar (2012) point out that public policies refer to "the set of actions that are carried out or implemented by governmental actors or by these in association with social actors (economic, civil) or by private and social actors who have been empowered or authorized by the government to do so" (p.17).

Szasz *et al.* (2003) point out that the gender approach can be approached from a relational dimension, that is, from social relations that are built based on social conditions that guide individual behavior, conditions, actors, and relations that are generated by the different spheres of action in which women and men participate, highlighting the school, work, social, political, religious and reproductive rights spheres, among others.

Table 1. Adolescent Reproductive Rights

Right to make decisions about my reproduction free of discrimination and violence.
The right to decide freely whether to have daughters or sons
Right to decide what kind of family I want to form
Right to determine how many children I want and the time between pregnancies
The right to exercise maternity with equal treatment in the family, educational, and work environments.
The right to comprehensive sex education throughout life
The right to access modern methods of contraception, including emergency contraception.
The right to access the benefits of scientific advances in sexual and reproductive health.

Source: Inter-American Institute of Human Rights (2008). Reproductive Rights are Human Rights. IDH. https://www.iidh.ed.cr/IIDH/media/1826/derechos_reproductivos_ddhh-2008.pdf

On the other hand, authors such as Stern (1997), Collado *et al.* (2008), and Ehrenfeld (2008) focus their analysis on the role of public policies on the issue of teenage pregnancy, highlighting the existence of an erroneous perception of the causality of the phenomenon, as well as its implications derived from the little impact that public policies and government programs have had on reducing pregnancy at an early age.

Considering all these elements, it is proposed that to advance in the development and formulation of public policies with a gender perspective in the prevention of adolescent pregnancy, it is necessary first of all to have a diagnosis of the State of this general problem, which makes it possible to identify and describe the socio-demographic situation and characteristics, the conditions and social situation of women, the nature of social relations, and to consider the differences between women and men, in addition to analyzing the factors that generate inequalities and social exclusion.

3.1 Adolescent pregnancy: Courses of action for the rights of adolescents.

In Mexico, in 2014, the National Strategy for the Prevention of Adolescent Pregnancy (ENAPEA) was carried out in coordination with 16 government agencies, international organizations, civil society organizations, and experts to make substantial progress on the issue with actions and strategies to reduce the number of teenage pregnancies nationwide (Inmujeres, 2014). The ENAPEA aims to reduce the number of pregnancies in Mexico through two main goals: to reduce to zero births in girls aged 10 to 14 years and to reduce the fertility rate of adolescents aged 15 to 19 years (TFA15-19) by 50% by 2030 (Inmujeres, 2021).

It is essential to highlight the efforts of the goals set by ENAPEA in the actions designed and implemented by the Interinstitutional Group for the Prevention of Adolescent Pregnancy (GIPEA) and at the state level through the State Groups for the Prevention of Adolescent Pregnancy (GEPEA).

The Hidalgo Strategy for the Prevention of Adolescent Pregnancy (EHPEA), under the responsibility of the state group GEPEA (2020), has the medium-term objective of strengthening the mechanisms for the fulfillment of the goals established in both the National Strategy (ENAPEA) and the State Strategy (EHPEA).

Among the actions carried out by the GEPEA (2020) are the following:

- 1.- To develop a computerized system for registering, following up, and monitoring care for girls and adolescent mothers and/or pregnant women under 15.
 - 2.- Incorporate civil society organizations to be part of the group.
 - 3.- To strengthen the capacities of the group members in the area of Human Rights.
- Strengthen comprehensive sexual education in secondary schools through the implementation of a methodological guide in the State.

Even though the existence of programs and strategies focused on the prevention of adolescent pregnancy and the gradual reduction of adolescent and child pregnancies, efforts have not been sufficient to address this public problem in depth. We are far from reaching the 2030 goal of reducing births to zero in girls aged 10 to 14 years and reducing the fertility rate of adolescents aged 15 to 19 years by 50%.

The problem of adolescent pregnancy and its prevention should be addressed from a multifactorial approach, considering that sexual and reproductive health is influenced by other factors that have not been thoroughly evaluated, such as the concept of new masculinities and responsible paternity, strategies should be generated from a gender perspective that considers the care of adolescent women and men, through multidisciplinary actions such as workshops, education, and training, comprehensive sexual education, human rights, campaigns in social networks, dissemination and disclosure of gender mainstreaming programs that provide a tangible and measurable response to the severe problem of early pregnancy.

Conclusions

Traditional approaches establish a relationship between teenage pregnancy and school dropout, indicating that young women drop out of educational institutions because of adolescent pregnancy. The literature review retrieved texts by Stern (1997, 2008, 2009, 2012). Likewise, relevant authors such as Villalobos-Hernández *et al.* (2015) and various international organizations such as the WHO (2020) agree that teenage pregnancies occur mainly in developing countries and populations with low socioeconomic strata. Stern constructs an

alternative approach in which he places as the main factors the enormous inequalities and gender relations.

In the case of the State of Hidalgo, education plays a crucial role in preventing early and unwanted pregnancies: it is effective when girls can access and attend school, can start their schooling at an early age, and stay in school longer, mainly through a supportive and welcoming school environment, thus avoiding expulsion, exclusion, and violence.

Although significant efforts have been made at the national and subnational levels to address the problem of adolescent pregnancy in Mexico, much remains to be done. The absence or little application of public policies designed and implemented with a gender perspective has not been sufficient.

Progress must be made in designing and implementing public policies or courses of action with a gender perspective, support, and commitment at all levels. These efforts should be focused on a multisectoral approach, strengthening gender mainstreaming and respect for the sexual and reproductive rights of adolescents.

References:

- Aguilar Villanueva, L. F. (2012) *Política Pública: Una visión panorámica*. United Nations Development Programme.
- World Bank (2019) *Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women aged 15-19)*. <https://datos.bancomundial.org/indicador/SP.ADO.TFRT>
- Buvinic, M., Valenzuela, J. P., Molina, T., and González, E. (1992). The Fortunes of Adolescent Mothers and Their Children: The Transmission of Poverty in Santiago, Chile. *Population and Development Review*, 18(2), 269. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1973680>. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1973680>
- Collado, M. E., Alva, R., Villa, L., López, E., González de León, D., & Schiavon, R. (2008). Unwanted pregnancy and abortion in adolescents: A challenge and a collective responsibility. *Género y Salud En Cifras*, 6(2), 17-30. <https://biblat.unam.mx/es/revista/genero-y-salud-en-cifras/articulo/embarazo-no-deseado-y-aborto-en-adolescentes-un-reto-y-una-responsabilidad-colectiva>. <https://biblat.unam.mx/es/revista/genero-y-salud-en-cifras/articulo/embarazo-no-deseado-y-aborto-en-adolescentes-un-reto-y-una-responsabilidad-colectiva>.

- Ehrenfeld, N. (2008). Pregnancy in adolescents: A topic with several controversies. *Gender and Health in Figures*, 6(1).
- United Nations Population Fund [UNFPA] (2020) *Socioeconomic consequences of adolescent pregnancy in Mexico*. UNFPA .
<https://mexico.unfpa.org/es/publications/folleto-consecuencias-socioecon%C3%B3micas-del-embarazo-en-adolescentes-en-m%C3%A9xico>
- Grupo Estatal para la Prevención del Embarazo en Adolescentes [GEPEA] (2020) Informe Ejecutivo de GEPEA Hidalgo, 2020.
https://www.gob.mx/cms/uploads/attachment/file/628539/Informe_GEPEA_Hidalgo_2020_FINAL.pdf
- Haub, C. (2010). 2010 World Population Data Sheet. *Population Reference Bureau*.
<https://www.prb.org/resources/2010-world-population-data-sheet/>
- Hernández Sampieri, R. and Mendoza Torres, C. (2018). *Research Methodology: Las Rutas Cuantitativa, Cualitativa y Mixta*. McGraw-Hill.
- INEGI (2020) *Average level of schooling of the population aged 15 years and over by State by sex, selected census years 2000 to 2020*.
https://www.inegi.org.mx/app/tabulados/interactivos/?px=Educacion_05&bd=Educacion
- Inmujeres (2014). *National Strategy for the Prevention of Adolescent Pregnancy (ENAPEA)*. Government of Mexico. <https://www.gob.mx/inmujeres/acciones-y-programas/estrategia-nacional-para-la-prevencion-del-embarazo-en-adolescentes-33454>
- Inmujeres (2021). *Estrategia Nacional para la Prevención del Embarazo en Adolescentes*. Government of Mexico. <http://www.gob.mx/inmujeres/acciones-y-programas/estrategia-nacional-para-la-prevencion-del-embarazo-en-adolescente>
- Inter-American Institute of Human Rights (2008). *Reproductive Rights are Human Rights*. IDH.
https://www.iidh.ed.cr/IIDH/media/1826/derechos_reproductivos_ddhh-2008.pdf
- World Health Organization [WHO] (2020). *Adolescent Pregnancy*.
<https://www.who.int/es/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/adolescent-pregnancy>
- Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development [OECD] (2017) *How does MEXICO compare to child well-being?* OECD Child Well-Being Data Portal Country Fact sheet. https://www.oecd.org/els/family/CWBBDP_Factsheet_MEX.pdf
- Ortiz Lazcano, A. (2016). Embarazo en universitarias, el caso de la UAEH, 2014. *RICSH .Revista Iberoamericana de las Ciencias Sociales y Humanísticas*, 4(8), 104.
<https://doi.org/10.23913/ricsh.v4i8.41>
- United Nations Development Programme [UNDP] (2015). *Índice de Desarrollo Humano para las entidades federativas, México 2015* (HDI in Mexico Series). United Nations.

<https://www.mx.undp.org/content/mexico/es/home/library/poverty/indice-de-desarrollo-humano-para-las-entidades-federativas--mexi.html>

Sen, A. (1999). *Development as freedom*. Oxford University Press.

Stern, C. (2012). *The "problem" of adolescent pregnancy. Contributions to a debate*.

Colegio de México. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt14jxqkf>

Stern, C. (1997). Adolescent pregnancy as a public problem: A critical view. *Salud Publica de Mexico*, 39(2), 137-143.

<https://saludpublica.mx/index.php/spm/article/view/5990>

Stern, C. (2009). Differences in adolescent pregnancy among population strata. In

Stern, C. and Herrera, G. (2008). *Adolescents in Mexico research, experiences, and strategies to improve their sexual and reproductive health*. El Colegio de México.

Szasz, I., Lerner, S. and Canales, A. (2003) *Aportes teóricos y desafíos metodológicos de la perspectiva de género para el análisis de los fenómenos demográficos*. Mexican Society of Demography

Villalobos-Hernández, A., Campero, L., Suárez-López, L., Atienzo, E. E., Estrada, F., & De la Vara-Salazar, E. (2015). Adolescent pregnancy and educational lag: Analysis of a national survey in Mexico. *Salud Publica de Mexico*, 57(2), 135.

<https://doi.org/10.21149/spm.v57i2.7409>